

Challenges and Pedagogical Practices of Science Teachers in Rural Palawan: Basis for the Development of a Context-Responsive Pre-Service Science Teachers' Training Program

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Article Details:

Received: 10 April 2026
Revised: 16 April 2026
Accepted: 25 April 2026
Published: 9 May 2026
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Recommended Citation:

Mosquito M. J. N. (2026). Challenges and Pedagogical Practices of Science Teachers in Rural Palawan: Basis for the Development of a Context-Responsive Pre-Service Science Teachers' Training Program. *The International Review of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1 (5), 276-292. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20094621>

Index Terms:

context-responsive teacher training, Palawan, pedagogical practices, phenomenology, rural science education, teacher challenges

Abstract. Science education is fundamental to cultivating scientifically literate citizens and fostering engagement with societal issues. In rural schools, however, this potential is constrained by persistent resource shortages, limited infrastructure, and uneven teacher preparation, which collectively diminish instructional quality. This study examined the challenges and pedagogical practices of 15 high school science teachers in rural Palawan through a qualitative-descriptive phenomenological design. Co-participants were purposively selected, and their narratives were gathered through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using Colaizzi's method. The analysis revealed six emergent themes describing instructional challenges: structural resource constraints, spatial and environmental constraints on teaching, curriculum and institutional pressures, learner preparedness and engagement barriers, socioeconomic and cultural contextual barriers, and professional vulnerability in rural teaching. Alongside these, five emergent themes highlighted adaptive pedagogical practices: deliberate instructional planning and resource design, active and responsive instructional approaches, classroom structuring and learner engagement, assessment and instructional adjustment, and professional and collaborative agency. Collectively, these interconnected themes illustrate how teachers sustain meaningful science learning despite material scarcity, curriculum congestion, and professional stress, demonstrating resilience, improvisation, and collaborative agency in their practice. Building on these insights, the study developed a 5-Day Context-Responsive Pre-Service Science Teacher Training Program designed to strengthen competencies in contextual awareness, resource-conscious planning, responsive pedagogy, assessment-driven instruction, and professional resilience. Grounded in authentic rural realities, the study contributes to advancing inclusive and equitable science education by informing teacher education, guiding institutional and policy reforms, and underscoring the importance of sustained support for rural schools and further research on the long-term impact of context-responsive preparation.

Introduction

Science education is central to innovation, economic growth, and societal progress in the twenty-first century. It equips learners with critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills needed to address global challenges such as climate change, public health crises, and rapid technological transformation (UNESCO, 2023; Langthaler & Mendez, 2023). In the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, science education must move beyond rote memorization and emphasize inquiry-based learning, creativity, and the application of knowledge to real-world contexts (Kunnath & Botes, 2025). International reports consistently highlight the need to strengthen science education systems, improve scientific literacy, expand access for marginalized groups, and promote transdisciplinary approaches (ISC, 2024; Schuck & Feser, 2022). Large-scale assessments further show that achievement in science is shaped by teacher quality,

curriculum alignment, socioeconomic conditions, and resource availability (Marôco, Harju-Lukkainen, & Rautopuro, 2024).

In the Philippines, reforms such as the K to 12 Curriculum and the MATATAG initiative have sought to enhance science learning outcomes (DepEd, 2024). However, national and international assessments reveal persistent challenges. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022 reported that only 23 percent of Filipino 15-year-olds reached the minimum proficiency level in science, ranking the country 77th out of 81 participants (OECD, 2023; CPBRD, 2024). Similarly, the National Achievement Test (NAT) results for 2023 and 2024 showed low proficiency levels across grade levels and regions, with mean percentage scores far below the 75 percent benchmark (DepEd-SDO Palawan, 2025; Tolentino, 2025). Students performed relatively better in problem-solving but struggled most with critical thinking, underscoring difficulties in applying conceptual understanding.

These disparities are more pronounced in rural and geographically isolated schools, where systemic inequalities constrain access to quality science education. In provinces such as Palawan, schools face logistical barriers, limited laboratory facilities, unstable internet connectivity, and shortages of qualified teachers (Añar, Barroso, & Manlagaylay, 2023; Duque, Rosario, & Dacles, 2021; Gregorio, 2025). Broader analyses attribute rural underperformance to resource limitations, socioeconomic constraints, and reduced access to effective instructional materials (Zamora & Dorado, 2021; Teves, Yap, & Chua, 2022). While these conditions pose challenges, rural communities also offer unique contextual resources such as ecological knowledge and community practices that can enrich science learning when effectively integrated. Teachers, however, must navigate complex instructional realities requiring adaptability, resourcefulness, and pedagogical flexibility. Given these realities, pre-service teacher education becomes critical for strengthening science instruction in rural schools. Effective preparation programs can equip future educators with pedagogical adaptability, contextual awareness, and culturally responsive strategies (Darling-Hammond et al., 2021). Nevertheless, current frameworks often fail to prepare novice teachers for the structural, instructional, and sociocultural complexities of rural classrooms (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023; Gregorio, 2025). Despite growing recognition of rural educational disparities, limited research has examined how science teachers' lived experiences and pedagogical adaptations can inform pre-service training. In response, this study explores the challenges and practices of science teachers in rural Palawan, generating contextually grounded insights to inform the design of a context-responsive pre-service science teacher training program. In doing so, it contributes to strengthening teacher preparation, supporting evidence-informed policy, and advancing inclusive, equitable, and high-quality science education for rural learners (UNESCO, 2023; Langthaler & Mendez, 2023).

Central Question

To gain a deep understanding of the lived experiences of science teachers in rural Palawan, this phenomenological study centers on one overarching question that guides the entire inquiry: *"How can the challenges and pedagogical practices of science teachers in rural Palawan inform the development of a context-responsive pre-service science teachers' training program?"* This central question aims to capture the essence of their experiences regarding their professional challenges and instructional and pedagogical practices.

Corollary Questions

The following corollary questions guided the researcher:

1. How do science teachers describe their challenges and pedagogical practices in delivering science education in rural Palawan?
2. What essential meanings can be formulated from their challenges and pedagogical practices in teaching science in rural Palawan?
3. What themes emerge from their challenges and pedagogical practices in delivering science education in rural Palawan?
4. How can these meanings and themes inform the development of a pre-service science teacher training program that is responsive to the realities of delivering science education in rural Palawan?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological design to examine the lived experiences of high school science teachers in rural Palawan, focusing on the challenges they encountered and the pedagogical practices they employed. A qualitative approach was appropriate because the objective was to capture how teachers interpret and make meaning of their professional realities in resource-constrained contexts (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Phenomenology was chosen to

uncover the essence of teaching science in rural schools by analyzing participants' experiential accounts and identifying shared structures of challenges and practices (Creswell & Poth, 2024).

Selection of Co-Participants

The study employed purposive sampling to select 15 high school science teachers from rural schools in SDO Palawan and SDO Puerto Princesa, with one teacher per school to ensure representation across varying levels of NAT performance in Science. NAT results provided contextual indicators of instructional conditions and resource environments. Purposive sampling was chosen to identify information-rich participants capable of offering detailed reflections on their experiences and practices, consistent with phenomenological research that values depth of lived experience over statistical generalization (Patton, 2015, as cited in Naeem et al., 2023; Creswell & Poth, 2024). The sample size aligns with Creswell and Poth's (2024) recommendation of 5–25 participants to achieve saturation. Eligible participants had at least five years of teaching experience, were currently teaching in rural or resource-limited schools, and were willing to provide detailed accounts of their instructional challenges and pedagogical practices. This strategy ensured diversity in rural teaching conditions while maintaining analytic depth.

Data Generation

Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews with purposively selected high school science teachers in rural Palawan. Each interview lasted 45–60 minutes and was conducted either face-to-face or online, depending on accessibility. The interview guide, reviewed by experts and piloted with a rural teacher, included professional background profiles, prompts on instructional challenges and pedagogical strategies, and reflections on pre-service teacher preparation. Open-ended questions encouraged detailed narration, while probing allowed clarification and elaboration.

With participants' consent, interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and anonymized using pseudonyms. Ethical approval was secured from the university research and development office, the Department of Education–SDOs of Palawan and Puerto Princesa, and participating schools. Participants were fully briefed, provided informed consent, and assured confidentiality, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any time.

To support clarity and coherence in manuscript preparation, the researcher responsibly used AI tools as language-support aids for phrasing and organization. These tools were used transparently, with all outputs critically reviewed and refined to preserve accuracy, contextual relevance, and fidelity to participants' voices. Data collection continued until saturation was reached, when no new significant statements emerged, and thematic structures stabilized.

Thematic Data Analysis

This study employed Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological analysis (1978) to examine the lived experiences of science teachers in rural Palawan. Colaizzi's method was chosen for its systematic procedure in transforming experiential accounts into structured thematic insights while remaining faithful to participants' voices.

The analysis followed Colaizzi's seven steps: (1) repeated reading of transcripts for holistic understanding, with bracketing to minimize researcher bias; (2) extraction of significant statements on instructional challenges, contextual constraints, and pedagogical practices; (3) formulation of meanings faithful to participants' descriptions; (4) clustering of meanings into themes, checked against transcripts for accuracy; (5) integration of themes into an exhaustive description of rural science teaching; (6) validation of this description through member-checking with participants; and (7) refinement into a fundamental structure representing the essence of the phenomenon.

To further enhance credibility and reliability, peer debriefing sessions with fellow researchers were conducted, enabling the critical examination of analytic decisions and thematic interpretations.

Results and Discussion

Challenges of Science Teachers in Rural Palawan

The accounts of co-participants reveal the layered realities of science teaching in rural schools, where difficulties extend beyond isolated incidents and reflect broader structural and contextual conditions. Teachers consistently described challenges related to limited resources, environmental and spatial constraints, institutional pressures, learner concerns, sociocultural factors, and professional vulnerability. These dimensions are interconnected, often occurring simultaneously, and collectively shape instructional decisions and student learning.

Emergent Theme 1: Structural Resource Constraints

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"At present, we only have books for Grade 7, which received new materials last year. Grades 8, 9, and 10 no longer have books. At times, the available books do not even align with the revised curriculum." (1.56)</i>	Absence and shortage of science books, modules, and learning materials hinder curriculum alignment, lesson delivery, and student comprehension.	Instructional & Laboratory Resource Scarcity
<i>"We have electricity, but no internet connection. Whenever we need to show something to the students, we download it in advance and play it offline." (11.25)</i>	Poor and unstable internet connectivity blocks access to online resources, limiting teachers' ability to integrate ICT in science teaching.	ICT & Utility Limitations
<i>"If resources are unavailable, students cannot access them. That is why I find ways to provide for myself and my learners. I often sacrifice and spend my own money to support my students." (4.20)</i>	Teachers are forced to spend their own money to make up for shortages of science materials and resources.	Teacher Personal Financial Burden

Table 1. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 1: Structural Resource Constraints

Science teachers in rural Palawan face three interconnected challenges: the lack of instructional and laboratory materials, unreliable electricity and internet, and the personal financial burden of covering shortages themselves. Textbooks, modules, and laboratory equipment are often incomplete or outdated, limiting students' opportunities for hands-on learning. Frequent brownouts and poor connectivity prevent the use of ICT tools and laboratories, while the absence of multimedia devices narrows teaching options. To cope, teachers often spend their own money on supplies, chemicals, or ICT equipment, adding financial and emotional strain to their work.

These findings show that resource scarcity is not just about missing materials but also about the inability to use existing ones due to weak infrastructure. Similar studies in the Philippines highlight chronic shortages and ICT limitations as persistent barriers to effective science instruction (San Luis & Villafranca, 2022; Aldea & Dayawon, 2025). In this context, structural resource constraints continually shape the realities of rural science teaching, forcing teachers to improvise and sacrifice personally while exposing the gap between policy expectations and classroom conditions.

Emergent Theme 2: Spatial and Environmental Constraints on Teaching

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"Another issue we face is the suspension of classes during bad weather. Many of our students come from other barangays or islands, so during the rainy season or typhoons, the LGU declares class suspensions. As a result, some laboratory hands-on activities are not implemented." (9.7)</i>	Bad weather and frequent class suspensions interrupt laboratory activities and science instruction.	Geographic Isolation and Environmental Vulnerability
<i>"When I first arrived at my school, I felt so sorry for my advisory class because the room felt like a chicken cage." (7.49)</i>	Makeshift classrooms resembling cages create poor and unsafe learning environments for science.	Inadequate, Unsafe, and Overcrowded Facilities

Table 2. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 2: Spatial and Environmental Constraints on Teaching

Beyond shortages of materials and utilities, teachers also face the realities of geography and school infrastructure. Remote school locations and geographic isolation make access difficult, while frequent typhoons, heavy rains, and landslide-prone terrain disrupt classes and damage laboratories. At the same time, facilities are often incomplete, unsafe, or overcrowded. Laboratories lack essential equipment, classrooms are poorly designed or makeshift, and student numbers frequently exceed 50 per room, limiting engagement and safety during experiments. These conditions create stressful environments that hinder effective science instruction and reduce opportunities for hands-on learning.

Spatial and environmental constraints are not occasional disruptions but recurring realities that shape the rhythm and quality of science teaching. Philippine rural education studies have long documented how isolation and vulnerability affect schooling conditions (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023; Quejada & Orale, 2018, as cited in Galut, 2025), while national assessments

highlight uneven infrastructure quality across geographically isolated schools (Navarro, 2024). Prior research also emphasizes that instructional effectiveness depends not only on the presence of laboratories but on their usability and safety (Pareek, 2019, as cited in Lansangan & Orleans, 2024). These accounts underscore how geography, environmental exposure, and infrastructural fragility continually frame the realities of science instruction, shaping when, where, and under what conditions learning can take place.

Emergent Theme 3: Curriculum and Institutional Pressures

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"I am not able to finish all the competencies. For me alone, there are always one or two competencies within the quarter that are left unattained. This happens because there are so many class disruptions—aside from school activities, there are now frequent suspensions." (11.33)</i>	A congested curriculum and misaligned competencies slow pacing, prevent the completion of lessons, and hinder the achievement of learning targets.	Curriculum Congestion & Time Constraints
<i>"You might be surprised that even if you are a science major, you can still be assigned to teach other subjects. For example, I am a science major, and although I teach science, I also handle TLE and values education." (11.75)</i>	Teacher shortages force science teachers to handle non-science subjects, reducing focus and quality of science instruction.	Administrative Load & Staffing Limitations

Table 3. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 3: Curriculum and Institutional Pressures

While resource scarcity and environmental fragility set the material and spatial limits of science teaching, teachers also described how curriculum design and institutional demands define the structural boundaries of their work. Congested curricula, misaligned competencies, and unsuitable performance tasks slowed lesson pacing and often left lessons unfinished. Excessive modules and the need to reteach foundational skills consumed limited instructional time, while cultural misalignment made it difficult to adapt standardized science activities to local contexts. At the same time, institutional pressures such as strict documentation checks, large class sizes, staffing shortages, and additional non-teaching tasks diverted teachers' attention from science. These overlapping demands compressed instructional space, leaving teachers overstretched and classrooms overcrowded.

Curriculum and institutional pressures are systemic conditions that regulate how science is taught. National critiques of the K to 12 framework highlight curriculum congestion and compressed timelines as barriers to effective delivery (Cordon & Polong, 2020; CPBRD, 2024), while rural studies emphasize lost instructional time and remediation demands as persistent challenges (San Luis & Villafranca, 2022; Aldea & Dayawon, 2025). Research also shows that standardized curricula often require contextual adaptation in rural and culturally distinct settings (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023). Gaps between ancillary workload and policy-to-practice further constrain teachers' instructional capacity, with non-teaching tasks consuming 55% of weekly hours and exceeding DepEd's 2-hour limit for ancillary work (EDCOM II, 2025). These pressures illustrate how curriculum expectations and institutional demands continually frame the realities of science teaching in Palawan, narrowing opportunities for meaningful learning and shaping the everyday rhythm of instruction.

Emergent Theme 4: Learner Preparedness and Engagement Barriers

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"I employ a variety of assessment tools, such as quizzes (multiple choice, matching type, true or false, explanation), performance tasks, and project-based activities. Examples include atomic structure models, cell models, laboratory activities, and brief reflections." (9.36)</i>	Teachers diversify assessment methods (quizzes, essays, role-playing, projects, lab reports, peer feedback, reflection) to address multiple intelligences and varied learner needs.	Formative Assessment & Feedback Practices
<i>"If the science subject is difficult for students, I use remediation in a tutor-type approach. I find a student who is good in science and assign them as a mentor. If it is just one or two students, I handle it myself. I ask the student to come to my office alone, and I provide a tutorial session for them." (4.34)</i>	Teachers provide one-on-one tutorials, peer mentoring, and after-class interventions to support struggling learners.	Remediation & Targeted Intervention Strategies

Table 4. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 4: Learner Preparedness and Engagement Barriers

Teachers in rural Palawan emphasized that even when resources, environments, and institutional structures are managed, science instruction still depends on learners' readiness and engagement. Abstract concepts, weak literacy foundations, language difficulties, and pandemic disruptions created comprehension gaps that slowed lesson pacing and required constant reteaching. Students often struggled with computation-heavy tasks, poor reading comprehension, and limited English proficiency, which reduced participation and made science appear more difficult. Alongside these comprehension challenges, teachers described barriers to engagement, including low motivation, short attention spans, absenteeism, and avoidance of demanding tasks. Traditional methods failed to sustain interest, while inquiry-based approaches consumed time and sometimes overwhelmed learners. These conditions reveal how uneven preparedness and fluctuating engagement continually shape the tempo and depth of science lessons.

Learner-related barriers are not occasional classroom issues but enduring realities that define instructional practice. Studies highlight how weak literacy and limited prior knowledge restrict students' ability to process scientific texts and solve problems (Cordon & Polong, 2020; Bai, 2023), while research on multilingual contexts shows that English-dominant curricula intensify comprehension difficulties when learners lack strong language foundations (Carrete-Marín et al., 2024; UNESCO, 2023). Pandemic disruptions further widened preparedness gaps, echoing findings that rural learners entered post-pandemic classrooms with diminished readiness for complex topics (San Luis & Villafranca, 2022; Aldea & Dayawon, 2025). Engagement instability, such as short attention spans, poor retention, and avoidance of challenging tasks, has similarly been documented as a barrier to sustained learning in rural science classrooms (Zinger et al., 2020; Rivera et al., 2023). In Palawan, these accounts underscore how comprehension gaps and motivational challenges converge, making science teaching a process of constant adaptation to uneven cognitive, linguistic, and behavioral landscapes.

Emergent Theme 5: Socioeconomic and Cultural Contextual Barriers

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"We regularly hold LAC sessions where we share effective teaching tactics, best classroom practices, and engage in short conversations about difficult themes to gain ideas from one another." (9.21)</i>	Teachers collaborate with colleagues through focus group discussions, LAC sessions, and mentorship to share strategies and improve science teaching.	Stakeholder Collaboration (Peer, Administrative, Community)
<i>"In rural areas where equipment and resources are lacking, teachers should be prepared to be resourceful and creative, and to relate themselves to the types of learners in the school or community." (1.77)</i>	Teachers adapt lessons creatively and resourcefully when faced with limited laboratory equipment, materials, electricity, or internet access.	Teacher Resourcefulness, Resilience, and Adaptability

Table 5. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 5: Socioeconomic and Cultural Contextual Barriers

Teachers in rural Palawan emphasized that science instruction is inseparable from the communities' socioeconomic and cultural realities. Poverty, hunger, and long travel distances were linked to absenteeism, dropouts, and disengagement, while livelihood demands such as fishing often took precedence over school attendance. Weak parental support further undermined project-based learning, with many students unable to submit outputs due to financial constraints or a lack of encouragement at home. These conditions disrupted classroom continuity and reduced participation, leaving teachers to adapt lessons around the pressures of everyday survival.

Cultural and religious contexts added another layer of complexity. Classrooms were marked by linguistic diversity, with students struggling across multiple mother tongues, Filipino and English. Language barriers slowed comprehension and required teachers to adjust communication styles, sometimes even learning students' dialects. Religious and cultural restrictions limited certain science activities, such as dissections, reducing opportunities for experiential learning. Diversity in socioeconomic background and unusual classroom behaviors further complicated inclusion, making instructional flow uneven and unpredictable.

Socioeconomic and cultural barriers, therefore, emerge as structural realities that actively mediate science teaching. Studies of rural education in the Philippines highlight how poverty and geographic isolation constrain access to education and learning outcomes (Bai, 2023; Navarro, 2024), while livelihood demands frequently disrupt instructional continuity (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023). Research also shows that teachers in remote schools must continually negotiate cultural and linguistic diversity as part of everyday practice (Quejada & Orale, 2018, as cited in Galut, 2025; Aldea & Dayawon, 2025). International work on rural STEM classrooms similarly underscores how community identities and cultural expectations shape what is possible in science education (Zinger et al., 2020; Rivera et al., 2023). These findings reveal that science teaching is community-embedded, in which economic hardship and cultural particularities intersect with classroom practice, shaping not only who is present but also how knowledge is communicated and experienced.

Emergent Theme 6: Professional Vulnerability in Rural Teaching

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"Before I was deployed, there was no orientation at all—no briefing, no training. The only training you could attend was once you were already there, and even then, it was not really about preparing for teaching in rural schools." (8.71)</i>	Pre-service and in-service teachers lack training in educational technology, subject-specific science content, and rural teaching strategies, leaving them unprepared for resource-poor contexts.	Insufficient Preparation for Rural Teaching Contexts
<i>"I was really frustrated. In my previous school, every room had a TV, a projector, electricity, and Wi-Fi. Then you come here, and there were times I just felt lazy or annoyed, thinking this is all I'll do, just walk ahead, because there are no books, no TV. It was frustrating." (8.77)</i>	Transition from well-equipped schools to resource-poor rural schools causes frustration, demotivation, and professional dissatisfaction.	Emotional & Professional Stress

Table 6. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 6: Professional Vulnerability in Rural Teaching

Teachers in rural Palawan described how professional vulnerability shapes their daily work, extending beyond instructional challenges to questions of preparation, identity, and well-being. Many entered rural schools without orientation or targeted training, leaving them unprepared for resource-poor contexts, diverse student populations, and shifting grade-level assignments. Accounts highlighted gaps in subject-specific seminars, limited exposure to educational technology, and inconsistent professional development opportunities. Teachers also spoke of culture shock when adapting to new communities and differences in teaching styles among colleagues, which complicated adjustment and consistency. These conditions made professional growth uneven and left teachers navigating rural realities largely on their own.

Emotional and professional stress compounded these preparation gaps. Isolation, scarce resources, and weak institutional support were repeatedly linked to frustration, demotivation, and exhaustion. Teachers found the transition from well-equipped urban schools to resource-poor rural contexts disorienting and discouraging, while logistical challenges, such as poor transportation and weak internet connectivity, added further strain. Some explicitly questioned their sustainability in the profession, reflecting how vulnerability extends into morale and identity. These experiences echo research showing that early-career teachers in remote schools often encounter a mismatch between pre-service preparation and lived realities (Solis Rodriguez, 2025; Galut, 2025), while national studies note unequal access to professional learning opportunities across regions (Navarro, 2024; CPBRD, 2024). International reports likewise emphasize that rural STEM teachers frequently lack ongoing training, mentoring networks, and technological upgrades compared to their urban counterparts (US GAO, 2025; UNESCO, 2023). In Palawan, vulnerability is not about incompetence but about heightened exposure to systemic inequities: insufficient preparation, limited support, and sustained emotional strain converge to test teachers' resilience and identity, making professional vulnerability a defining condition of rural science teaching.

Pedagogical Practices of Science Teachers in Rural Palawan

Following the accounts of challenges, teachers also described the pedagogical practices that sustain science instruction in rural schools. These practices are not isolated techniques but broader instructional responses shaped by resource scarcity, environmental fragility, institutional demands, learner preparedness, and community contexts.

Teachers spoke of deliberate planning, localization and contextualization, active and responsive approaches, classroom structuring, assessment adjustments, and professional collaboration. Each dimension overlaps in practice, portraying a teaching context in which science learning is sustained through adaptive, creative, and community-responsive strategies.

Emergent Theme 1: Deliberate Instructional Planning and Resource Design

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"In teaching science, my typical day involves preparing my DLL, lesson plan, and the set of activities to be accomplished within 45 minutes to an hour. We need to follow the lesson plan, address the competencies, align our activities, and, of course, conduct the assessment." (11.11)</i>	Teachers rely on structured lesson plans, MELCs, DLLs, and curriculum frameworks (Bloom's taxonomy, PISA, 5Es/7Es models) to ensure systematic and aligned science instruction.	Structured and Curriculum-Aligned Planning

<i>"The learners are already familiar with the community setting here, so they easily relate to the lessons. As much as possible, our activities are contextualized or localized so that learners do not feel burdened, especially since many of them struggle with science." (1.04)</i>	Teachers contextualize science lessons to local community settings, daily experiences, and socioeconomic realities to make learning relatable and accessible.	Localization and Contextualization of Science Learning
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Table 7. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 1: Deliberate Instructional Planning and Resource Design

Teachers in rural Palawan emphasized that effective science instruction begins with deliberate planning and resource preparation, where lesson plans, curriculum frameworks, scaffolding strategies, and recall checks serve as anchors for systematic teaching. Many deliberately slowed pacing to prioritize comprehension over coverage, repeating activities in varied forms to strengthen retention, while resource preparation compensated for shortages of books, technology, and laboratory equipment through handouts, worksheets, improvised tools, and community-sourced materials. Visual aids such as posters, charts, and videos were used to make abstract concepts more accessible, and laboratory equipment was prepared in advance to ensure smooth implementation of hands-on activities. Planning extended into localization and contextualization, with teachers connecting lessons to community settings, cultural practices, and socioeconomic realities, substituting household items or recycled resources for missing materials, and indigenizing instructions to align with traditions and everyday experiences.

Research underscores the importance of these practices in resource-constrained contexts. Clear curriculum alignment through lesson plans and frameworks has been shown to safeguard instructional quality even when materials are improvised (Masalimova et al., 2024). Studies of rural classrooms in the Philippines confirm that resource scarcity is widespread, but teachers often respond with innovation, such as designing their own materials, sourcing from communities, and contextualizing lessons to local realities (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023; Gregorio, 2025; Urma & Callo, 2023). Place-based approaches further highlight how connecting science to everyday experiences and cultural practices enhances relevance and engagement (Yemini, Engel, & Ben-Simon, 2023). In Palawan, these accounts show that foresight, flexibility, and creativity are not supplementary but essential to sustaining meaningful science learning under constraint.

Emergent Theme 2: Active and Responsive Instructional Approaches

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"One effective strategy I use is hands-on, learner-centered activities such as experiments, group projects, and simulations. These allow students to actively explore concepts and see the real-world applications of what they are learning." (13.66)</i>	Teachers emphasize hands-on, activity-based, and experiential science learning to make lessons engaging, enjoyable, and accessible.	Experiential, Inquiry-Based & Collaborative Science Learning
<i>"The most effective approach is when you associate games with the lesson. When there are games, the students become active and truly participative." (7.59)</i>	Teachers integrate game-based learning and interactive activities to capture student interest, sustain participation, and make science enjoyable.	Engagement-Oriented Instructional Techniques
<i>"For me, effective strategies include differentiated instruction and cooperative learning. Differentiated instruction addresses different learning needs, and students can showcase their abilities based on their skills." (2.20)</i>	Teachers apply differentiated instruction to accommodate diverse learning styles, abilities, and socioeconomic backgrounds, ensuring inclusivity in science learning.	Differentiated and Learner-Responsive Instruction
<i>"To integrate ICT, I use students' cellphones in class for interactive games like Mentimeter or the Lumi application. These tools are helpful in making lessons more engaging." (2.26)</i>	Teachers integrate ICT tools (multimedia, videos, animations, simulations, PowerPoint, Google Slides) to make science lessons interactive, engaging, and accessible.	ICT-Enabled Science Instruction

Table 8. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 2: Active and Responsive Instructional Approaches

Instruction in rural science classrooms often takes the form of active, participatory methods that go beyond lecture delivery. Teachers described how learning becomes more accessible when students manipulate materials, conduct simple

experiments, or engage in inquiry tasks that gradually build toward complex ideas. Community settings were treated as living laboratories, such as mangroves, coastlines, and school grounds, which became spaces for exploration, while improvised experiments using household items ensured continuity despite resource gaps. Engagement was sustained through gamification, interactive activities, and playful strategies that transformed abstract concepts into memorable experiences. Responsiveness also meant tailoring lessons to diverse learning styles and socioeconomic backgrounds, balancing simplified tasks for struggling learners with enrichment for advanced students. ICT integration further expanded possibilities, with multimedia, simulations, and digital resources used to visualize processes and complement hands-on work. These accounts portray science teaching as dynamic and adaptive, where instruction is continuously recalibrated to sustain participation and comprehension.

Studies on inquiry-based and collaborative learning approaches consistently foster critical thinking and problem-solving, yet their effectiveness depends on careful scaling in resource-limited contexts and on teacher scaffolding with technology integration to support diverse educational settings (Roslan et al., 2023; Soomro, Soomro, & Memon, 2025). Evidence also shows that gamification and interactive formats strengthen motivation and performance, aligning with teachers' emphasis on engagement-oriented strategies (Qureshi et al., 2023). In education, differentiation creates engaging and challenging experiences that improve engagement and achievement by customizing instruction, content, and assessment to meet the needs of diverse learners. (Goyibova et al., 2025). ICT integration, meanwhile, illustrates pragmatic adaptation: science teachers' strong TPACK competence and high self-efficacy in technology use, coupled with evidence that higher levels of ICT integration positively correlate with pupils' learning outcomes, underscore confidence in aligning digital tools with pedagogy to enhance engagement and achievement (Gacayan, 2025; Pamisa & Hinacay, 2025). Rural teachers often rely on offline downloads, shared devices, and low-tech blended alternatives to overcome infrastructure gaps (Urma & Callo, 2023). These practices show science teaching in rural Palawan as a responsive craft that is active, inclusive, and context-sensitive, where both learner diversity and limited resources shape pedagogy.

Emergent Theme 3: Classroom Structuring and Learner Engagement

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"I provide positive reinforcement and encouragement by acknowledging students' efforts, ideas, and achievements. This boosts their confidence and motivates them to engage more actively in class." (13.71)</i>	Teachers sustain motivation through positive reinforcement, praise, recognition, and constructive feedback.	Behavioral Structuring and Motivational Strategies

Table 9. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 3: Classroom Structuring and Learner Engagement

Keeping science lessons active and responsive also required teachers to deliberately shape the classroom environment. Accounts highlighted how engagement was sustained not only through activities but through careful structuring of behavior, motivation, and rapport. Monitoring group work, clarifying misconceptions, and handling misbehavior constructively were described as everyday practices, while reward systems—points, badges, certificates, even small tokens—turned attendance and participation into sources of excitement. Praise and recognition reinforced confidence, and teachers often adjusted lessons mid-class, switching activities or inserting quick experiments to re-focus distracted learners. Engagement was further supported through situational tasks grounded in real-life experiences, creative techniques such as singing or storytelling, and one-on-one discussions that fostered trust and inclusion. These strategies reveal how classroom structuring and learner engagement are not peripheral concerns but central pedagogical acts that make science instruction possible in rural schools.

The emphasis on deliberate engagement resonates with broader scholarship. Collaborative and motivational structures have been shown to significantly influence student performance (Qureshi et al., 2023), while learner-centered teaching increases student engagement, thereby improving academic achievement. When academic achievement increases for all students, positive social change occurs (Cain, 2020). In the Philippine context, relational and motivational strategies such as attendance rewards, improvisational humor, and flexible pacing reflect adaptive responses to absenteeism, socioeconomic constraints, and cultural diversity (Cabrales & Pacala, 2023; Gregorio, 2025). Rather than relying on authoritarian discipline, teachers emphasized relational competence, proximity monitoring, and encouragement, echoing Barredo's (2025) argument that effective classroom management in resource-constrained settings depends on inclusion and rapport. At a systems level, these practices connect directly to national concerns about science literacy and PISA performance (CPBRD, 2024; Cordon & Polong, 2020), since sustained engagement is the foundation for inquiry and higher-order learning. Classroom structuring in rural Palawan thus emerges as intentional work: cultivating conditions where learners feel seen, motivated, and capable of participating meaningfully in science learning.

Emergent Theme 4: Assessment and Instructional Adjustment

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"I employ a variety of assessment tools, such as quizzes (multiple choice, matching type, true or false, explanation), performance tasks, and project-based activities. Examples include atomic structure models, cell models, laboratory activities, and brief reflections." (9.36)</i>	Teachers diversify assessment methods (quizzes, essays, role-playing, projects, lab reports, peer feedback, reflection) to address multiple intelligences and varied learner needs.	Formative Assessment & Feedback Practices
<i>"If the science subject is difficult for students, I use remediation in a tutor-type approach. I find a student who is good in science and assign them as a mentor. If it is just one or two students, I handle it myself. I ask the student to come to my office alone, and I provide a tutorial session for them." (4.34)</i>	Teachers provide one-on-one tutorials, peer mentoring, and after-class interventions to support struggling learners.	Remediation & Targeted Intervention Strategies

Table 10. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 4: Assessment and Instructional Adjustment

Alongside classroom structuring, teachers highlighted assessment as a central mechanism for guiding science instruction and ensuring that learning remains responsive. Accounts described diagnostic checks, short quizzes, and performance-based tasks as routine practices to monitor readiness and comprehension. Volcano models, dioramas, comic skits, and creative projects were valued for allowing students to apply concepts in practical ways, while rubrics and checklists ensured fairness and consistency. Teachers diversified methods—combining essays, role-playing, laboratory reports, and peer feedback—to accommodate varied learning styles and abilities. Importantly, assessment was not treated as a static measure but as a cycle that fed directly into instructional adjustment. Tutorials, peer mentoring, and after-class interventions supported struggling learners, while modular learning, messaging apps, and home visits provided continuity for those absent or working. Language barriers and comprehension difficulties were addressed through simplified instructions, pacing adjustments, and scaffolding, with differentiated tasks balancing support for struggling learners and enrichment for advanced students. These practices reveal assessment as inseparable from adaptation, functioning more as a tool for sustaining inclusion and progress than as a record of achievement.

Scholarly discussions reinforce this adaptive view of assessment. Authentic, inquiry-driven evaluations are increasingly recognized as central to building higher-order skills (Masalimova et al., 2024), while differentiated strategies that adapt content, process, and assessment foster engagement and inclusivity across diverse classrooms (Marymount University, 2024). In the Philippine context, teachers' emphasis on performance tasks and progressive questioning responds directly to national concerns about science literacy and persistent gaps in higher-order competencies (CPBRD, 2024; Cordon & Polong, 2020). Remediation practices such as slowing lessons, revisiting fundamentals, and providing one-on-one or peer tutoring align with Cabrales and Pacala's (2023) description of rural teaching as relational and context-bound, in which assessment results prompt targeted intervention. Technology-mediated continuity, such as modular learning and messaging apps, illustrates how evaluation extends into flexible delivery modes, ensuring that learning does not collapse under socioeconomic constraints. As equity-focused frameworks emphasize, assessment is not merely evaluative but also serves as adaptive navigation; participatory approaches that allow learners to actively engage in the evaluation process link curriculum intent with learner reality and foreground equity as central to instructional practice (El-Khoury, 2023; Alordiah & Arisi, 2025).

Emergent Theme 5: Professional and Collaborative Agency

Representative Co-Participant Statement	Formulated Essential Meaning	Subtheme
<i>"We regularly hold LAC sessions where we share effective teaching tactics, best classroom practices, and engage in short conversations about difficult themes to gain ideas from one another." (9.21)</i>	Teachers collaborate with colleagues through focus group discussions, LAC sessions, and mentorship to share strategies and improve science teaching.	Stakeholder Collaboration (Peer, Administrative, Community)
<i>"In rural areas where equipment and resources are lacking, teachers should be prepared to be resourceful and creative, and to relate themselves to the types of learners in the school or community." (1.77)</i>	Teachers adapt lessons creatively and resourcefully when faced with limited laboratory equipment, materials, electricity, or internet access.	Teacher Resourcefulness, Resilience, and Adaptability

Table 11. Thematic Structure of Emergent Theme 5: Professional and Collaborative Agency

Sustaining science teaching in rural schools was not described as an individual effort alone but as something strengthened through collaboration and professional resilience. Teachers spoke of collegial exchanges in focus group discussions, mentorship, and Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions where strategies were shared and refined. Parents and communities were engaged to source local materials, provide feedback, and contextualize lessons, while barangay health centers and local leaders were tapped as partners in enriching science activities. Administrative support through resources, orientation, and training was also valued, alongside collegial assistance in ICT integration. These accounts highlight how professional agency is relational, built through networks of trust and shared responsibility across peers, families, and communities.

At the same time, agency was expressed through resourcefulness and adaptability. Teachers improvised instructional materials, relocated classes outdoors when needed, and encouraged students to bring improvised tools to sustain experiments. Dedication and emotional readiness were repeatedly emphasized, with teachers framing resilience as both a professional and personal commitment to continue teaching despite scarcity. Some pursued advanced studies to strengthen their practice, while others stressed the importance of immersion and flexibility for pre-service teachers entering rural contexts. These reflections align with scholarship that views collaboration and innovation as essential in resource-limited classrooms (Qureshi et al., 2023; Masalimova et al., 2024), and with place-based approaches that emphasize community partnerships in making science meaningful (Yemini et al., 2023; Cabrales & Pacala, 2023). They also echo findings that resilience and relational competence are critical for sustaining teaching in constrained environments (Gregorio, 2025; Barredo, 2025). Professional and Collaborative Agency thus emerges as a dual construct: relational, through networks of support, and adaptive, through resourcefulness and resilience. Together, these dimensions show how rural science teachers transform limitations into opportunities, ensuring that science education remains accessible and meaningful.

Exhaustive Description of Science Teaching in Rural Palawan

Science teaching in rural Palawan unfolds within persistent constraints that shape both pedagogy and professional identity. Scarcity of laboratory materials, outdated textbooks, and unstable ICT infrastructure compel teachers to improvise, contextualize lessons with local resources, and often use personal funds to sustain instruction. Physical and environmental challenges, such as overcrowded classrooms, geographic isolation, and disruptions from flooding or transport, further complicate lesson continuity, while institutional demands, such as congested curricula, limited time, and heavy documentation, force constant modifications to plans. Learners enter with varying levels of preparedness, influenced by poverty, livelihood responsibilities, and limited home support, requiring differentiated strategies and culturally responsive approaches. Teachers themselves face vulnerability in the form of emotional strain and isolation, yet resilience emerges through collaboration, reflection, and adaptive practice.

Despite these realities, instruction remains deliberate and responsive: lessons are localized, inquiry-based strategies are improvised, engagement techniques sustain participation, and assessment serves as a guide for adjustment rather than mere evaluation. Professional practice extends beyond the classroom through collaboration with peers, administrators, parents, and communities, underscoring resourcefulness and persistence as defining qualities of rural science teaching.

Essential Structure of Science Teaching in Rural Palawan

From this integrated description, the essential structure of the phenomenon may be articulated as follows:

"Rural science teaching in Palawan is a sustained effort to deliver meaningful, contextually relevant science education within material, environmental, institutional, and sociocultural constraints, through adaptive, resourceful, and resilient professional practice."

At its core, the experience reflects teachers' enduring commitment to making science learning possible despite persistent limitations.

Proposed Output of the Study

This study proposes Teaching Science Where It Matters Most: A 5-Day Context-Responsive Pre-Service Science Teachers' Training Program, designed to bridge the preparation gap between pre-service training and the realities of rural science classrooms.

Grounded in the emergent themes of the phenomenological analysis, the program reframes rural teaching not as a deficit but as a context requiring deliberate planning, adaptive instruction, responsive assessment, contextual sensitivity, and professional resilience.

Day	Focus / Theme	Key Content Focus	Strategies / Activities	Expected Output
Day 1	Understanding the Rural Teaching Ecology	Structural, environmental, socioeconomic, and cultural realities; community assets.	Case analysis of rural school scenarios; simulation of teaching under resource constraints; community asset mapping; reflective journaling.	Context analysis reports, adapted MELC activities and reflective essays on professional stance.
Day 2	Deliberate Instructional Planning Under Constraint	MELC-aligned planning; low-cost activities; pacing adjustments; feasibility checks.	Workshop on contingency lesson planning; design of resource-conscious activities; peer critique of lesson feasibility.	4-layer contingency lesson plans; prototype low-cost science activities; feasibility evaluation notes.
Day 3	Active and Responsive Instruction	Inquiry tasks without lab equipment; differentiated strategies; engagement techniques.	Microteaching sessions, design of differentiated tasks, gamification, storytelling exercises and peer feedback.	Inquiry-based lesson prototypes; differentiated activity sets; engagement strategy portfolio.
Day 4	Assessment and Instructional Adjustment	Diagnostic and formative tools; rubrics; remediation strategies; equity-oriented feedback.	Construction of diagnostic quizzes; rubric-building workshop; role-play of remediation sessions; peer review of assessment tools.	Diagnostic and formative assessment tools; analytical rubrics; remediation plans tailored to learner diversity.
Day 5	Professional Resilience and Identity Formation	Coping systems; support networks; resilience planning; teaching portfolio.	Reflection circles, resilience planning workshop, creation of teaching portfolios and identity articulation exercises.	Structured resilience plans; contextualized teaching portfolios; professional identity statements.

Table 12. The Proposed Training Program of the Study

The five-day training program is intentionally sequenced to reflect the realities of rural science teaching, progressing from contextual awareness to professional identity formation. Day 1 establishes a foundation by immersing participants in the ecology of rural classrooms, reframing constraints as complex teaching environments, and identifying community assets. Day 2 builds on this awareness through contingency-based instructional planning, equipping participants to anticipate disruptions while safeguarding conceptual integrity. Day 3 shifts to classroom delivery, emphasizing inquiry, differentiation, and engagement strategies that sustain participation in heterogeneous, resource-limited settings. Day 4 integrates assessment as a diagnostic and adaptive tool, guiding instructional adjustments and remediation to ensure equity and inclusivity. Finally, Day 5 consolidates professional resilience and identity, enabling pre-service teachers to articulate coping systems, collaborative networks, and a clear stance toward rural science teaching. Collectively, the progression ensures that participants acquire not only techniques but also the adaptive professionalism required to sustain meaningful science education in rural contexts.

By translating teachers' lived experiences into structured preparation, the program equips pre-service science teachers to design context-responsive lessons, implement adaptive instruction, use assessment to guide adjustment, and sustain professional agency. As a replicable model for teacher education, it offers practical implications for curriculum design, professional development, and policy, positioning rural realities not as deficits but as contexts that demand deliberate, resilient, and responsive practice.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study demonstrates that science teaching in rural Palawan is profoundly shaped by contextual realities that diverge from idealized models of instruction. Structural resource limitations, environmental challenges, institutional demands, and diverse learner needs collectively define the conditions under which teachers plan and deliver lessons. Within these constraints, rural science teachers enact adaptive professional practice. They contextualize scientific concepts, improvise materials, differentiate instruction, and employ interactive strategies to sustain meaningful learning despite persistent shortages.

Findings also reveal that instructional challenges and pedagogical practices are inseparable: the strategies teachers employ emerge directly from the conditions they face. Pedagogy in rural schools is therefore not abstract or theoretical but deeply practical, grounded in the realities of resource scarcity, learner diversity, and institutional pressures. Finally, the study underscores the necessity of context-responsive preparation for pre-service science teachers. Competence in contextual analysis, adaptive planning, responsive instruction, assessment-informed adjustment, and professional resilience is essential for delivering equitable and meaningful science education in rural communities.

Implications

The findings carry significant implications for teacher education, professional development, and education policy. First, teacher preparation programs must move beyond assumptions of stable infrastructure and adequate resources. Integrating context-responsive modules into pre-service curricula can better equip future teachers to anticipate and manage the realities of rural classrooms. Second, professional development initiatives should emphasize adaptive instructional planning, resource improvisation, and equity-oriented assessment practices, ensuring that in-service teachers continue to refine strategies that respond to local conditions.

At the policy level, the study highlights the importance of systemic support for rural educators. Investments in infrastructure, resource provision, and community partnerships can reduce the burden of improvisation and allow teachers to focus on pedagogy rather than survival strategies. Equally critical is recognizing resilience and collaborative agency as professional competencies. Supporting networks of teachers, administrators, and communities can strengthen science education in rural areas and foster sustainable professional practice.

In sum, rural science teaching in Palawan illustrates both the challenges and possibilities of delivering education under constraint. By embedding context-responsive preparation into teacher education and policy frameworks, science teaching can be sustained as meaningful, inclusive, and resilient—even in the most resource-limited settings.

Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges the support of Palawan State University, the Department of Education, the Schools Division Offices of Palawan and Puerto Princesa, and the science teacher co-participants, whose insights and cooperation provided the foundation for this study. The encouragement of colleagues, students, family, and friends, together with the guidance of academic mentors and institutional leaders, sustained the author throughout the research process. Any remaining errors or omissions are the sole responsibility of the author.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

This study draws on both primary qualitative data and secondary literature. Interview transcripts and coded data were generated and analyzed by the author. Due to confidentiality agreements and ethical considerations, these primary data are not publicly available but may be accessed upon reasonable request from the author, subject to restrictions that protect participant privacy. All secondary data are derived from publicly available sources, as cited in the reference list.

References

- Añar, L. E., Barroso, C. J. V., & Manlagaylay, M. P. (2023). The performance of basic education learners in the National Achievement Test. *Journal for ReAttach Therapy and Developmental Diversities*, 6(9s), 1520–1535. <https://jrtdd.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1931>

- Aldea, K. Q., & Dayawon, M. A. (2025). Rural science education during and beyond COVID-19: teachers' strategies and prospects from a Philippine perspective. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 14(4), 2846. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v14i4.30446>
- Alordiah, C. O., & Arisi, R. (2025). Toward a critical pedagogy of assessment integrating social studies education: The proposed socio-critical assessment integration framework (SCAIF). *Journal of Research Initiatives*, 8(5), Article 7. Fayetteville State University Digital Commons. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.uncfsu.edu/jri/vol8/iss5/7>
- Bai, N. (2023). Educational challenges in the Philippines. Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS). Retrieved from <https://pids.gov.ph/details/news/in-the-news/educational-challenges-in-the-philippines>
- Barredo, B. (2025). Classroom management challenges of elementary education student teachers. *The International Journal of Learning in Higher Education*, 33, 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2327-7955/CGP/v33i02/25-41>
- Cabrales, P. S., & Pacala, F. A. (2023). Science education in the Philippine countryside: A phenomenological study. *Indonesian Journal of Education Teaching and Learning*, 3(1). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371043522_SCIENCE_EDUCATION_IN_THE_PHILIPPINE_COUNTRY_SIDE_A_PHENOMENOLOGICAL_STUDY
- Cain, C. M. (2020). Understanding the use of learner-centered teaching strategies by secondary educators (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University). Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies, 8865. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/8865>
- Carrete-Marín, Núria & Domingo-Peñafiel, Laura & Simó Gil, Núria. (2024). Teaching materials for rural schools: challenges and practical considerations from an international perspective. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*. 7, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2024.100365>
- Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department. (2024). The Philippines' performance in the 2018 and 2021 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (Facts in Figures No. 2024-11). <https://cpbrd.congress.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/FF2024-11-Philippines-Perf-in-the-2018-and-2021-PISA.pdf>
- Cordon, J. M., & Polong, J. D. B. (2020). Behind the Science literacy of Filipino students at PISA 2018: A Case study in the Philippines' Educational System. *Integrated Science Education Journal*, 1(2), 70-76. <https://doi.org/10.37251/isej.v1i2.59>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2024). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2021). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2024). DepEd Order No. 010, s. 2024: Institutionalization of the MATATAG K to 10 curriculum. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DO_s2024_010.pdf
- Department of Education, Schools Division of Palawan. (2025). NAT 10 results for School Year 2022-2023 [Unpublished raw data]. Curriculum Implementation Division.
- Duque, N. C., Rosario, L. A., & Dacles, D. M. (2021). Demographic profile and academic performance of a Philippine rural public elementary school: Basis for assistance program. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 10(1), 1–15. <https://pubs.sciepub.com/education/10/1/1/index.html>
- EDCOM II. (2025). Understanding teacher workload as a systemic issue (Policy brief). Education Commission II. Retrieved from https://edcom2.gov.ph/media/2025/03/EDCOM2_Policy-Brief_Ancillary-Workload.pdf
- El-Khoury, E. (2023). Equity and assessments. In York's Community of Practice for DEDI in Teaching and Learning (Ed.), *Designing equitable assessments in teaching & learning*. Ecampus Ontario Pressbooks. Retrieved from <https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/dedi/chapter/what-is-equity-in-assessments/>
- Gacayan, J. B. (2025). Teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) competence and technology integration self-efficacy beliefs for science teaching. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(7), 798–811. <https://doi.org/10.69569/jip.2025.323>
- Galut, M. N. A. (2025). Surviving in the trails: Teacher's lived experiences in remote areas. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 10, Article 1456269. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2025.1456269>
- Gregorio, M. (2025). Enhancing of science education in rural areas of the Philippines. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5282807>
- Goyibova, N., Muslimov, N., Sabirova, G., Kadirova, N., & Samatova, B. (2025). Differentiation approach in education: Tailoring instruction for diverse learner needs. *MethodsX*, 14, 103163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2025.103163>
- International Science Council. (2024). Science education and the ISC: Report of the Consultative Group on Science Education to the ISC Governing Board. <https://council.science/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Science-Education-and-the-ISC.pdf>

- Kunnath, A. J., & Botes, W. (2025). Transforming science education with artificial intelligence: Enhancing inquiry-based learning and critical thinking in South African science classrooms. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 21(6), em2655. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/16532>
- Langthaler, M. & M. J. (2023). Inequalities in education from a global perspective: Theoretical approaches, dimensions and policy discussions. *ideas.repec.org*. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/zbw/oefseb/34.html>
- Lansangan, R. V., & Orleans, A. V. (2024). Exploring Filipino students' critical thinking skills: Basis for enhancement of science laboratory class delivery. *Science Education International*, 35(3), 281–290. <https://doi.org/10.33828/sei.v35.i3.11>
- Marôco, J., Harju-Lukkainen, H., & Rautopuro, J. (2024). Worldwide predictors of science literacy in lower-secondary students: a TIMSS 2019 analysis. *International Journal of Science Education*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2024.2394239>
- Marymount University. (2025). Differentiating instruction for diverse learners in K–12 education. <https://marymount.edu/blog/differentiating-instruction-for-diverse-learners-in-k-12-education/>
- Masalimova, A. R., Zheltukhina, M. R., Sergeeva, O. V., Kosarenko, N. N., Tsomartova, D. A., & Smirnova, L. M. (2024). Science teaching in BRICS: A systematic review of pedagogical approaches and challenges. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 20(4), em2432. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/14434>
- Naeem, M., Ozuem, W., Howell, K., & Ranfagni, S. (2023). A Step-by-Step process of thematic analysis to develop a conceptual model in qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069231205789>
- Navarro, A. (2024). School Infrastructure in the Philippines: Where Are We Now and Where Should We Be Heading?. *Philippine Institute for Development Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.62986/rps2024.06>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The state of learning and equity in education. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/53f23881-en>
- Pamisa, A. T., Jr., & Hinacay, J. J. D. (2025). Teachers' ICT integration in science teaching and learning outcomes. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 8(9), 798–811. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v8-i09-42>
- Qureshi, M. A., Khaskheli, A., Qureshi, J. A., Raza, S. A., & Yousufi, S. Q. (2023). Factors affecting students' learning performance through collaborative learning and engagement. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(4), 2371–2391. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.1884886>
- Rivera, S., Kiiza, I., Kavanagh, K., DeWaters, J., Galluzzo, B., & Ramsdell, M. (2023). Challenges and opportunities for STEM teachers in rural schools: A case study. *Thresholds in Education*, 46(3), 420–432. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1435566>
- Roslan, S., Wahab, N. A., & Jalal, F. (2023). Inquiry-based learning in Southeast Asian classrooms: Teachers' perspectives and practices. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 9(2), 145–164. <https://doi.org/10.1163/23641177-bja10036>
- San Luis, J.C. & Villafranca, M.R. (2022). Looking through the lens of rural science teachers in the new normal setting. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 3(1), 74–96. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352864>
- Schuck, P., & Feser, M. S. (2022). Science education as a human right: A systematic review of the literature. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 10(3), 338–351. <https://doi.org/10.30935/scimath/11967>
- Solis Rodriguez, J. (2025). A Systematic Review of the Recent Empirical Literature on Math and Science Teacher Recruitment and Retention. *Education Sciences*, 15(8), 1073. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15081073>
- Soomro, R. B. K., Soomro, A. B., & Memon, I. (2025). Inquiry-based science teaching and its impact on critical thinking and problem-solving skills: A meta-analysis of STEM education. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6365963/v1>
- Teves, J. M. M., Yap, S. A., & Chua, U. C. (2022). Contrasting profiles of low-performing mathematics students in public and private schools in the Philippines: Insights from machine learning. *Journal of Intelligence*, 10(3), 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jintelligence10030061>
- Tolentino, A. J. (2025). NAT 2024 results show 'low proficiency' among Grade 12 students across all regions. Explained PH. <https://www.explained.ph/2025/03/nat-2024-results-show-low-proficiency-among-grade-12-students-across-all-regions.html>
- UNESCO. (2023). Global Education Monitoring Report 2023: Technology in education. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000385678>
- Urma, C. R., & Callo, E. C. (2023). Pedagogical challenges and teaching practices of multigrade teachers in rural public elementary schools. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 10(12), 219–226. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.1012.16017>
- US Government Accountability Office. (2025). STEM Education: Selected Federal Initiatives, Challenges, and Approaches to Supporting Rural Populations (Report GAO-25-107371). <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-25-107371>
- Yemini, M., Engel, L., & Ben-Simon, A. (2023). Place-based education — a systematic review of literature. *Educational Review*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2023.2177260>
- Zamora, C. M. B., & Dorado, R. A. (2021). Rural–urban education inequality in the Philippines using decomposition analysis. *Journal Article*, 3939. University of the Philippines Los Baños. <https://www.ukdr.uplb.edu.ph/journal-articles/3939>

Zinger, D., Haymore Sandholtz, J., & Ringstaff, C. (2020). Teaching Science in Rural Elementary Schools: Affordances and Constraints in the age of NGSS. *The Rural Educator*, 41(2), 14-30. <https://doi.org/10.35608/ruraled.v41i2.558>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.

